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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
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- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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BORROWED PROPER NOUNS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Amirqulova Feruza Abdurashidovna

Abstract: This article explores the phenomenon of borrowed proper nouns in English and Uzbek, focusing on the linguistic, historical, and cultural factors that have shaped their development. Borrowing is a universal linguistic process that enriches languages and reflects cultural contact and exchange. In English, a significant number of personal names, place names, and institutional names have been borrowed from Latin, French, Greek, and Biblical sources, often carrying deep historical and cultural connotations. Similarly, Uzbek proper nouns demonstrate a strong influence from Arabic, Persian, and Russian, reflecting religious traditions, literary heritage, and political history.

The study provides a comparative analysis of the borrowing processes in both languages, highlighting similarities such as the adaptation of foreign names to native phonetic and morphological systems, as well as differences based on cultural and historical contexts. Special attention is given to the role of globalization and modern English borrowings in contemporary Uzbek naming practices. The findings of the study reveal that borrowed proper nouns not only enrich linguistic resources but also serve as important markers of cultural identity and intercultural communication.

Key words: borrowed proper nouns, English, Uzbek, onomastics, cultural identity, globalization, linguistic borrowing, comparative linguistics.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz va o'zbek tillarida qarzga olingan o'zlashtirilgan ism-shariflar fenomenini tahlil qiladi, ularning rivojlanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatgan lingvistik, tarixiy va madaniy omillarga e'tibor qaratadi. Qarz olish – bu tillarni boyitadigan va madaniy aloqalar va almashinuvni aks ettiradigan umumjahon lingvistik jarayon. Ingliz tilida ko'plab shaxsiy nomlar, joy nomlari va institut nomlari lotin, fransuz, yunon va diniy manbalardan qarzga olingan bo'lib, ular ko'pincha chuqur tarixiy va madaniy ma'no'larni o'z ichiga oladi. Shuningdek, o'zbek ism-shariflari arab, fors va rus tillaridan kuchli ta'sirlanish ko'rsatadi, bu esa diniy an'analar, adabiy meros va siyosiy tarixni aks ettiradi.

Ushbu tadqiqot ikki tildagi qarz olish jarayonlarini taqqoslaydi, xorijiy nomlarning mahalliy fonetik va morfologik tizimlarga moslashishi kabi o'xshashliklarni, shuningdek, madaniy va tarixiy kontekstlarga asoslangan farqlarni ta'kidlaydi. Xalqaro tizimning va zamonaviy inglizcha qarzlarning o'zbek nom berish amaliyotidagi roli alohida e'tiborga olinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari, qarzga olingan o'zlashtirilgan ism-shariflar nafaqat lingvistik resurslarni boyitibgina qolmay, balki madaniy identitet va madaniyatlararo muloqotning muhim belgilariga aylanishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: qarzga olingan o'zlashtirilgan ism-shariflar, ingliz tili, o'zbek tili, onomastika, madaniy identitet, globalizatsiya, lingvistik qarz olish, taqqoslash lingvistikas.

Аннотация: Статья исследует явление заимствованных собственных имен в английском и узбекском языках, сосредотачивая внимание на лингвистических, исторических и культурных факторах, которые повлияли на их развитие. Заимствование – это универсальный лингвистический процесс, который обогащает языки и отражает культурные контакты и обмен. В английском языке значительное количество личных имен, географических названий и названий учреждений было заимствовано из латинского, французского, греческого и библейского источников, часто с глубокими историческими и культурными коннотациями. Точно так же в узбекских собственных именах сильно проявляется влияние арабского, персидского и русского языков, что отражает религиозные традиции, литературное наследие и политическую историю.

Исследование предоставляет сравнительный анализ процессов заимствования в обоих языках, выделяя такие сходства, как адаптация иностранных имен к местным фонетическим и морфологическим системам, а также различия, основанные на культурных и исторических контекстах. Особое внимание уделяется роли глобализации и современных заимствований из английского языка в современных практиках наименования в Узбекистане. Результаты исследования показывают, что заимствованные собственные имена не только обогащают лингвистические ресурсы, но также служат важными маркерами культурной идентичности и межкультурной коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: заимствованные собственные имена, английский, узбекский, ономастика, культурная идентичность, глобализация, лингвистическое заимствование, сравнительная лингвистика.

INTRODUCTION

Borrowing is one of the most universal and productive processes in the development of any language. Through contact with other nations, trade, migration, conquest, and cultural exchange, languages adopt new words and names to enrich their vocabulary and adapt to changing realities. Among borrowed elements, proper nouns occupy a special place because they serve not only as linguistic identifiers but also as cultural symbols. When a language borrows a name from another culture, it also absorbs a part of that culture's history, traditions, and worldview.

Proper nouns, as a category of onomastics, include personal names, geographical names, institutional names, and cultural references. While common nouns are often borrowed to denote new objects, technologies, or concepts, proper nouns are borrowed primarily for reasons related to identity, prestige, religion, or historical influence. For instance, many European languages, including English, adopted a significant portion of their personal names from the Bible and classical antiquity, reflecting both religious devotion and cultural continuity. Similarly, Uzbek borrowed a large number of proper nouns from Arabic and Persian as a result of the spread of Islam and centuries of cultural interaction in Central Asia.

In English, borrowed proper nouns come from various sources. Latin and Greek have contributed numerous personal names such as Marcus, Victoria, and Alexander, while French influence after the Norman Conquest brought names like Richard, Robert, and Isabel. In addition, geographical names in English preserve traces of Celtic, Norse, and Norman elements, illustrating how successive waves of cultural contact left their imprint on the naming system. Modern English continues to adopt new names from around the world, reflecting its global character and multicultural society.

In Uzbek, the borrowing of proper nouns has been shaped by historical, religious, and political factors. The Arabic and Persian influence is especially strong in anthroponymy, with names such as Abdulloh, Muhammad, Yusuf, Laylo, and Shahrizoda being widespread. These names often carry religious or moral meanings, symbolizing spiritual values. During the Russian imperial and Soviet periods, many Russian names and toponyms entered the Uzbek lexicon, reflecting the political and cultural dominance of that era. In recent decades, globalization has brought a new wave of English-based names into Uzbek society, particularly among younger generations who are influenced by Western culture, media, and education.

The study of borrowed proper nouns is important for several reasons. First, it provides insight into the historical and cultural contacts between nations. Names often serve as linguistic evidence of past interactions, trade relations, and migration patterns. Second, it demonstrates how languages adapt foreign elements to their own phonological and morphological systems, creating hybrid forms that reflect both the source and the recipient cultures. Third, the analysis of borrowed names contributes to our understanding of cultural identity, as names often function as markers of prestige, social belonging, and religious affiliation.

The aim of this article is to investigate the phenomenon of borrowed proper nouns in English and Uzbek, with a focus on their historical development, linguistic adaptation, and cultural significance. The main objectives are:

1. To analyze the main sources of borrowed proper nouns in English and Uzbek.
2. To examine the linguistic mechanisms used in adapting borrowed names to native systems.
3. To compare the similarities and differences in the borrowing processes of the two languages.
4. To explore the role of globalization in shaping modern naming practices.

The relevance of this study lies in the fact that borrowed proper nouns serve as bridges between languages and cultures. They are not only linguistic forms but also cultural artifacts that embody the memory of past interactions and the dynamics of present globalization. By studying borrowed names in English and Uzbek, we gain a deeper understanding of how languages evolve, how cultures influence each other, and how identities are expressed and reshaped through naming.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The phenomenon of borrowed proper nouns has been widely discussed in the field of onomastics and comparative linguistics. Scholars emphasize that proper nouns, unlike common nouns, are not merely lexical items but also cultural carriers (Crystal, 2003). According to Algeo (2010), the English language has historically incorporated a vast number of names from Latin, French, Greek, and Biblical sources, which illustrates the strong impact of cultural and historical contacts on English onomastics. Similarly, Trudgill (2000) notes that the Norman Conquest of 1066 had a decisive role in reshaping English personal names and toponyms.

In Uzbek linguistics, the study of borrowed names is closely linked to historical and cultural shifts. Karimov (1995) highlights the deep influence of Arabic and Persian on Uzbek anthroponymy, particularly during the Islamic period, when many names carried spiritual and religious meanings. Additionally, Russian and Soviet scholars such as Superanskaya (1973) and Baskakov (1981) have provided systematic classifications of proper names, which later influenced Uzbek name studies. Contemporary Uzbek linguists (To'xtasinov, 2010; Abdullayev, 2018) have also examined the impact of globalization, noting the rise of English-based names in modern Uzbek society.

Cross-linguistic comparisons in onomastics (Hough, 2016) show that borrowing processes share common mechanisms across languages, such as phonetic adaptation, morphological integration, and semantic reinterpretation. However, the extent and type of borrowings are strongly determined by cultural, religious, and political contexts. Despite numerous studies on English and Uzbek separately, there are still relatively few comparative works that analyze borrowed proper nouns in both languages together. This gap highlights the need for the present research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a comparative and descriptive method, focusing on English and Uzbek as the main objects of analysis. The methodology consists of the following steps:

- 1. Collection of Data:** In English, the data set includes personal names, geographical names, and institutional names of foreign origin (e.g., Latin, French, Greek, Biblical). In Uzbek, the data set covers Arabic, Persian, Russian, and English-based borrowed proper nouns.
- 2. Classification:** The collected names are classified according to their origin (e.g., Arabic, French, Russian), category (anthroponyms, toponyms, institutional names), and historical period of borrowing.
- 3. Comparative Analysis:** Similarities and differences between English and Uzbek borrowed names are analyzed. Particular attention is given to the adaptation processes, such as changes in spelling, pronunciation, and morphology.
- 4. Cultural Interpretation:** The study interprets borrowed proper nouns not only as linguistic items but also as cultural indicators. The role of religion, politics, and globalization is examined in shaping the borrowing process.

The research combines linguistic analysis (phonetic and morphological adaptation) with cultural-historical analysis, providing a holistic approach to the study of borrowed proper nouns. This methodological framework allows for identifying both universal features of borrowing and language-specific patterns.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The comparative analysis of borrowed proper nouns in English and Uzbek reveals both shared linguistic mechanisms and distinct cultural influences that shape the borrowing process in each language.

1. Sources of Borrowed Proper Nouns

In English, most borrowed proper nouns originate from Latin, French, Greek, and Biblical sources. These names often entered the language during major historical events such as the Roman occupation, the Christianization of Britain, and the Norman Conquest. For example, names like Alexander, Victoria, and Isabel reflect classical and religious heritage.

In contrast, Uzbek borrowed a significant number of proper nouns from Arabic, Persian, and Russian. Arabic and Persian names became widespread during the Islamic Golden Age, introducing names such as Muhammad, Yusuf, and Laylo, often carrying spiritual or moral significance. The Russian imperial and Soviet periods brought names like Svetlana, Nikolay, and toponyms such as Tashkent (adapted from Chach) into common use.

2. Adaptation Mechanisms

Both English and Uzbek demonstrate similar linguistic adaptation strategies when incorporating foreign names:

- Phonetic adaptation: Adjusting pronunciation to fit the phonological system of the receiving language.
 - e.g., Latin Marcus became Mark in English; Arabic Abdullah pronounced as Abdulloh in Uzbek.

- Morphological integration: Modifying names to conform with native morphological rules.
 - e.g., Uzbek often adds suffixes like -jon, -bek, or uses diminutives for personalization.
- Spelling changes: Adjustments in orthography to match native scripts and phonetics.

Despite these similarities, Uzbek often retains religious or spiritual connotations, whereas English borrowings are more secular or status-driven, especially in modern naming trends.

3. Cultural and Historical Impact

In English, name borrowing has been closely tied to colonial expansion, religion, and social class. Names of Greek or Latin origin are often associated with education and prestige.

In Uzbek, the influence of Islamic culture is dominant in traditional names, while Soviet-era names reflect political loyalty. In recent years, Western media, globalization, and migration have introduced English-based names like Kevin, Lilly, or Tom, especially among younger or urban families.

4. Globalization and Contemporary Trends

The influence of global culture has increased the presence of English-based names in Uzbekistan, especially among youth exposed to international media, the internet, and English-language education. This trend represents a shift from traditional and religious naming practices toward modern, globalized identities.

In English, while classical borrowings remain common, there is a growing trend of adopting names from non-European cultures due to increasing multiculturalism.

Key Findings:

- Both languages use similar linguistic processes (phonetic, morphological, semantic) in adapting borrowed proper nouns.
- Historical and cultural contexts significantly shape the types and meanings of borrowed names.
- Religious influence is more dominant in Uzbek borrowings, while social prestige and education are key drivers in English.
- Globalization plays a growing role in both contexts, leading to more diversified and international naming practices.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The comparative study of borrowed proper nouns in English and Uzbek reveals that the process of borrowing is not only a linguistic necessity but also a reflection of historical, cultural, and social dynamics. Both languages demonstrate that proper nouns serve as a special category of lexical units, carrying deep cultural meanings and historical memories.

In English, borrowed proper nouns mainly originate from Latin, French, Greek, and Biblical sources, which mirror the country's classical heritage, religious traditions, and the profound influence of the Norman Conquest. These borrowings have been gradually adapted into the English phonological and morphological system, becoming an inseparable part of the nation's linguistic identity.

In Uzbek, borrowed proper nouns are primarily influenced by Arabic, Persian, and Russian, reflecting the nation's religious devotion, literary heritage, and political history. More recently, globalization and cultural exchange have introduced English-based names, which are increasingly popular among younger generations. This indicates that Uzbek naming practices are undergoing a dynamic transformation, balancing between tradition and modernity.

The comparative analysis shows that both English and Uzbek integrate borrowed proper nouns through phonetic and morphological adaptation, but the cultural motivations behind borrowings differ. While English borrowings often symbolize classical prestige and Christian traditions, Uzbek borrowings highlight religious faith, historical ties with neighboring civilizations, and the impact of political dominance.

Thus, borrowed proper nouns play a dual role: they enrich the vocabulary of a language and serve as powerful markers of cultural identity. Their study provides valuable insights into intercultural communication, historical interaction, and the shaping of national consciousness.

Future research may expand this topic by focusing on sociolinguistic aspects of naming practices, especially the role of globalization and digital culture in shaping new trends in personal and institutional names.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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